

A Deep Search for Venus Co-orbital Asteroids

Petr Pokorný (Catholic University of America)

Figure 1. Density of asteroids per square degree in heliocentric ecliptic coordinates considering a population of 1,000,000 asteroids co-orbiting with Venus. In these coordinates the Sun is in the center and the ecliptic is at $y = 0$. The position of Venus is shown as a white dot at $(-44.85, 0)$. This image shows that there is a cavity around Venus, while the highest density of asteroids is at the other side of the Sun, i.e., at the anti-Venus point. (From [4], with permission)

Venus has recently been discovered to share its orbit with a ring of dust. This circumsolar ring of dust was imaged independently by two spacecraft: *HELIOS A/B* [1] and *STEREO A/B* [2]. *HELIOS* was able to estimate the radial and latitudinal extent of the ring by flying through it, while *STEREO* imaged its structure from 1 AU. Earlier work by Pokorný & Kuchner [3] showed that none of the currently observed small body populations in the Solar System are able to produce dust that evolves into a circumsolar structure of such a shape and magnitude. To solve this problem, Pokorný & Kuchner [3] modeled the effects of a hypothetical population of asteroids co-orbiting with Venus on

low-eccentricity and low-inclination orbits. The total amount of dust in Venus’s circumsolar dust ring was estimated to be equivalent to a 2-kilometer asteroid ground to dust. There are currently five known Venus co-orbitals: 2001 CK₃₂, 2002 VE₆₈, 2012 XE₁₃₃, 2013 ND₁₅, and 2015 WZ₁₂. All of these asteroids have highly eccentric orbits that cross Earth’s orbit, however, and are not able to contribute to the dust ring.

We (Petr Pokorný, Mark J. Kuchner, and Scott S. Sheppard) conducted a five-day twilight search for Venus co-orbital asteroids [4] to test our ring-origin hypothesis in September

Figure 2. *Left*: Distribution of 439,620 simulated Venus co-orbital asteroids as they would appear on 23 September at 23:30 UTC (gray dots) and 21,185 asteroids that were in our field of view during our five-day survey (orange circles). The black line represents the ecliptic, the red dot is the position of Venus on 23 September at 23:30 UTC. *Right*: The same as the left panel but now zoomed in to $210 < RA < 340$ and $-25 < Dec. < -5$. In total, our DECam survey was able to observe 4.82% of the entire population of hypothetical Venus co-orbitals. While the DECam field of view is approximately circular, the position of orange circles is not confined into circular areas. This is due to the fact that we stacked five days of data and that each asteroid has a different drift in RA and Declination (From [4], with permission)

2019, using a deep and wide survey with the Dark Energy Camera (DECam; mainly funded by the US Department of Energy) on the Víctor M. Blanco 4m Telescope at Cerro Tololo International Observatory. We detected three known near-Earth asteroids, but no Venus co-orbitals. Since Venus is inside Earth's orbit, the observing geometry provides only a short window during twilight that allows us to see kilometer-sized asteroids. Despite this, we were able to search 35 unique square degrees to 21 mag in the r band. By modeling hypothetical Venus co-orbital asteroids, we estimate that our survey probed 5% of the entire population that would be brighter than 21 mag. Depending on the properties of

the asteroids, our survey was sensitive to bodies larger than 400–900 meters in diameter. Despite finding no Venus co-orbitals, our survey was able to narrow down the upper limit for the number of asteroids larger than 400–900 meters in diameter to $N = 18 (+30/-14)$. This number is important for follow-up surveys and studies of the dynamical evolution of Venus co-orbitals.

Our survey was defined through extensive modeling, which allowed us to pick the most favorable observing time and geometry. Using models from [3], we simulated millions of hypothetical Venus co-orbital asteroids using six asteroid

types (S, M, E, C, P, D) to determine the variation of the asteroid magnitude with respect to position in the night sky. These types represent a broad range of albedos (0.04–0.45) and have well-determined asteroid phase functions, which are necessary to estimate the asteroid brightness with respect to the Sun-asteroid-Earth phase angle [5]. Observers usually try to keep this angle close to zero (i.e., observation at opposition) to maximize the amount of light reflected from the asteroid. This is only possible for objects that orbit beyond the orbit of Earth, while asteroids like those we sought can easily have phase angles higher than 90° . Our modeling showed that the best observing strategy is to 1) look close to the ecliptic about 45° away from the Sun, 2) avoid looking in the proximity of Venus, given the cavity in the asteroid density that the planet creates in its vicinity, and 3) look for objects that are moving faster than 90 arcseconds per hour (the average drift was 130 arcseconds per hour). Findings (1) and (2) are summarized in Figure 1.

Figure 1 provides a simplified model that does not take into account the position of Earth with respect to Venus, the Sun, and hypothetical co-orbital asteroids. Once we got the results of our five-day survey with the exact time of the observation and knowledge of the position of Earth with respect to Venus and the Sun, we performed another simulation in which the observing geometry matched precisely the one of our survey. This is shown in Figure 2, which depicts the distribution of the hypothetical Venus co-orbitals in RA and Declination on 23 September 2019. Thanks to our pre-observation modeling, we were able to sample almost 5% of the entire observable population in our five-day survey.

What does the non-detection of Venus co-orbital asteroids tell us? Using Poisson statistics we were able to obtain the limits for the population that can be present in the Solar System without being detected. The 1σ interval represents 4–48 asteroids with diameters larger than 400–900 meters that are able to avoid detection by our survey. This upper limit is supported by a recent survey by the Zwicky Transient Facility [6] that was less sensitive (19.5 mag) and also found no Venus co-orbital asteroids. When we extrapolate our upper limit to asteroids with diameters larger than 2 km, our survey predicts that fewer than 6 asteroids of that size are currently co-orbiting with Venus (this is the upper limit for very low albedo asteroids, e.g., C-types). Such a number of asteroids is quite small and makes the connection between the dust ring and the Venus co-orbital challenging. This leads to the following possible implications: (1) Venus co-orbitals might be non-reflective at the observed phase angles; (2) Venus co-orbitals have a very low albedo ($<1\%$); or (3) the Venus co-orbital dust ring has a source other than asteroids co-orbiting Venus. To shed more light on these implications a long-term survey is needed.

References

- [1] [Leinert, C. & Moster, B. 2007, A&A, 472, 335](#)
- [2] [Jones, M. H., Bewsher, D., & Brown, D. S. 2013, Sci, 342, 960](#)
- [3] [Pokorný, P. & Kuchner, M. 2019, ApJL, 873, L16](#)
- [4] [Pokorný, P., Kuchner, M., & Sheppard, S. 2020, PSJ, 1, 47](#)
- [5] [Shevchenko, V. G., et al. 2016, P&SS, 123, 101](#)
- [6] [Ye, Q., et al. 2020, AJ, 159, 70](#)